

ROLE OF SELF-HELP GROUPS IN PROMOTING WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE BODOLAND TERRITORIAL REGION OF ASSAM

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Abstract

Self-help groups (SHGs) have become vital instruments for empowering marginalized communities, especially rural women, by enhancing access to finance, skills, and entrepreneurship opportunities. Beyond financial inclusion, SHGs foster self-reliance, leadership, and decision-making within households and communities. In the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR) of Assam, an area marked by economic underdevelopment and gender inequality, SHGs play a pivotal role in enabling women to overcome barriers related to credit access, education, and market participation.

This paper examines the contribution of SHGs to women's entrepreneurship in the BTR through a comprehensive review of existing studies. It highlights how SHG participation enhances women's financial independence, entrepreneurial competence, and social mobility while simultaneously reshaping gender norms. However, despite measurable progress, several structural barriers persist, including inadequate infrastructure, limited market linkages, and entrenched sociocultural constraints that restrict the long-term sustainability of SHG-led enterprises.

The study emphasizes that strengthening institutional support, capacity building, and market integration is essential to amplify the impact of SHGs on women's economic empowerment. It concludes that while SHGs have significantly advanced women's entrepreneurship in the BTR, strategic policy interventions and sustained support systems are critical for realizing their full transformative potential in regional economic development.

Keywords: *Self-help groups, women entrepreneurship, empowerment, Bodoland Territorial Region, Assam*

1. Introduction

The growing recognition of women's contributions to economic development and social transformation underscores their importance as entrepreneurs, particularly in developing countries (Brush et al., 2009). In India, women constitute nearly half of the population, and

their active participation is critical for the nation's holistic development. Failing to harness women's potential not only limits progress but also results in the underutilization of half of the country's human resources. This neglect poses challenges across various sectors, including education, the economy, society, and politics.

Women's entry into entrepreneurship in India has undergone significant evolution. Traditionally, women were engaged in businesses related to household activities, such as pickle making, papad manufacturing, and weaving. However, in recent decades, women have ventured into diverse fields, including engineering, electronics, and renewable energy (Khanka, 2005). Despite these advancements, women in India continue to face significant challenges in business due to societal norms that often position them as subordinate to men. As women entrepreneurs challenge these traditional gender roles, they contribute to economic growth and reshape societal perceptions of gender and leadership (Audretsch et al., 2007). Nevertheless, persistent barriers such as limited access to finance, education, and markets, compounded by entrenched social structures, remain formidable obstacles (Kabbara, 2024).

Self-help groups (SHGs) have emerged as a promising solution to many of these challenges, particularly within marginalised communities. SHGs are voluntary collectives where members pool their savings, access credit, and engage in income-generating activities (Suneetha, 2012). These groups empower women by helping them overcome financial barriers, acquire entrepreneurial skills, and build social capital, thereby enabling them to start and grow their businesses (Patola & Sinha, 2005). Moreover, SHGs provide women without formal education or entrepreneurial experience the opportunity to gain self-confidence, improve decision-making abilities, and develop problem-solving skills (Charantimath, 2016).

In rural India, SHGs have become instrumental in fostering women's entrepreneurship. Recognizing their potential, the Indian government has implemented various initiatives, including the Swarnajyoti Gram Swarojgar Yojana, the National Rural Livelihood Mission, and the Deendayal Antodaya Yojana. These programs promote entrepreneurship by encouraging group savings, mutual decision-making, and structured meetings within SHGs. Additionally, the SHG Bank Linkage Programme, pioneered by NABARD, has successfully expanded financial inclusion, evolving from a simple banking outreach initiative to a comprehensive livelihood promotion and poverty alleviation program.

The Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR) of Assam offers a unique context for studying women's entrepreneurship through SHGs. This region, characterized by ethnic diversity,

socioeconomic disparities, and a predominantly tribal population, faces significant developmental challenges. Women in the BTR grapple with limited access to education, financial institutions, and persistent gender discrimination. Empowering women in this region through entrepreneurship is critical for enhancing their economic independence and contributing to the overall socio-economic development of the region (Barman & Chanu, 2017).

This study explores how SHGs foster women's entrepreneurship in the BTR by examining the experiences of women entrepreneurs and assessing the role of SHGs in overcoming barriers, building capacities, and promoting economic empowerment. A literature review approach is employed to investigate the status and challenges of women's entrepreneurship in the region, along with the impact of SHGs in facilitating growth.

2. Status of Women Entrepreneurship in the Bodoland Territorial Region

The development of women's entrepreneurship in the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR) of Assam has gained considerable attention in recent years. The BTR, comprising the four districts of Kokrajhar, Chirang, Baksa, and Udalguri, has a population of approximately 3,151,097, according to the 2011 Census. Women constitute around 49% of this population. However, the literacy rate among women in the region, at 58.27%, falls below both the national average of 64.64% and Assam's average of 66.27%, indicating a significant portion of women in the BTR remain illiterate (Census, 2011).

Agriculture dominates the economy of the BTR, with minimal urbanization and limited industrial development. This reliance on agriculture, combined with the region's industrial backwardness, contributes to overall economic stagnation. The promotion of women's economic empowerment through entrepreneurship is essential to overcoming these challenges and fostering sustainable growth.

Encouraging women's entrepreneurship in the BTR is vital for enhancing their economic independence and improving the region's socio-economic standing. Empowering women through entrepreneurial ventures can lead to sustainable economic growth, create employment opportunities, and enhance living standards. There is growing recognition that fostering women's entrepreneurship in the BTR can help bridge gaps in literacy and development while promoting greater gender equality and economic resilience (Barman & Chanu, 2017).

In addition to agricultural entrepreneurship, there are opportunities for women in the BTR to engage in sectors such as cottage industries, handloom, and handicrafts, capitalizing on the

region's rich cultural heritage. To realize this potential, it is necessary to strengthen local entrepreneurship ecosystems, improve access to financial resources, and provide targeted skill development programs for women.

One key indicator of entrepreneurship growth in the BTR is the number of registered Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Table 1 and Figure 1 illustrate the district-wise MSME registrations from April 1, 2007, to March 31, 2016. A significant variation exists across districts, with some experiencing no registrations in specific years. The highest number of registrations occurred in 2008–09, with 178 units, while the lowest was recorded in 2011–12, with 37 units. Among the districts, Udalguri had the highest percentage of registered units (32.18%), whereas Kokrajhar had the lowest (14.67%).

Table 2: District-wise Growth of Women Entrepreneurs in the MSME Sector in BTR, Assam (2007-2016)

Table 1: Number of Units Registered in the MSME Sector in BTR, Assam (2007–2016)

Year	Kokrajhar (units)	Chirang (units)	Baksa (units)	Udalguri (units)	Total (units)
2007-2008	17 (21.52%)	00 (0%)	48 (32.65%)	77 (52.38%)	142 (100%)
2008-2009	35 (19.66%)	13 (7.30%)	59 (33.15%)	71 (39.89%)	178 (100%)
2009-2010	20 (20.20%)	10 (10.64%)	35 (37.23%)	34 (36.17%)	99 (100%)
2010-2011	06 (7.69%)	04 (5.13%)	35 (44.87%)	33 (42.31%)	78 (100%)
2011-2012	08 (21.62%)	21 (56.76%)	04 (10.81%)	04 (10.81%)	37 (100%)
2012-2013	11 (24.44%)	10 (22.23%)	11 (24.44%)	13 (28.89%)	45 (100%)
2013-2014	07 (8.86%)	39 (49.37%)	31 (39.24%)	02 (2.53%)	79 (100%)
2014-2015	07 (9.59%)	53 (72.60%)	06 (8.22%)	07 (9.59%)	73 (100%)
2015-2016	08 (10%)	52 (65%)	00 (0%)	20 (25%)	80 (100%)
Total	119 (14.67%)	202 (24.91%)	229 (28.24%)	261 (32.18%)	811 (100%)

Source: District Industries and Commerce Centres (DICC)s of the four districts in BTR.

Fig 1: Registration Trend of MSME Units in BTR, Assam

Women's participation in the MSME sector remains notably low in the BTR. Only 286 units were registered between 2007 and 2016, accounting for 35% of the total and representing a mere 0.02% of the female population in the region (Census, 2011). This highlights the minimal involvement of women in entrepreneurial ventures. The highest number of female-led registrations occurred in 2007–08, with 79 units, while the lowest was in 2012–13, with only 9 units. District-wise, Udalguri led with 109 registered units (38.11%), while Chirang had the fewest at 33 units (11.54%).

Table 2: District-wise Growth of Women Entrepreneurs in the MSME Sector in BTR, Assam (2007–2016)

Year (as of March 31)	Kokrajhar (units)	Chirang (units)	Baksa (units)	Udalguri (units)	Total (units)
2007-2008	17 (21.52%)	00 (0%)	29 (36.71%)	33 (41.77%)	79 (100%)
2008-2009	12 (15.58%)	04 (5.19%)	19 (24.68%)	42 (54.55%)	77 (100%)
2009-2010	06 (20%)	04 (13.33%)	12 (40%)	08 (26.67%)	30 (100%)
2010-2011	02 (5.72%)	01 (2.86%)	21 (60%)	11 (31.42%)	35 (100%)
2011-2012	04 (30.77%)	07 (53.85%)	00 (0%)	02 (15.38%)	13 (100%)
2012-2013	02 (22.22%)	01 (11.11%)	02 (22.22%)	04 (44.45%)	09 (100%)
2013-2014	03 (18.75%)	06 (37.50%)	07 (43.75%)	00 (0%)	16 (100%)
2014-2015	03 (25%)	06 (50%)	01 (8.33%)	02 (16.67%)	12 (100%)
2015-2016	04 (26.67%)	04 (26.67%)	00 (0%)	07 (46.66%)	15 (100%)

Total	53 (18.53%)	33 (11.54%)	91 (31.82%)	109 (38.11%)	286 (100%)
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Source: District Industries and Commerce Centres (DICC)s of the four districts in BT

Figure 2: Registration Trend of Women-led MSME Units in BTR, Assam

3. Objectives of the Study

The primary objectives of this paper are:

1. To study the role of self-help groups in fostering and promoting women's entrepreneurship within the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR).
2. To identify the specific challenges that self-help groups face in supporting women's entrepreneurship in the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR).

4. Role of Self-Help Groups in Promoting Women’s Entrepreneurship in Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR)

Research both in India and globally highlights the transformative role of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) in fostering women’s entrepreneurship. In the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR), SHGs have been critical in empowering women to engage in business activities. These groups not only provide financial inclusion but also serve as platforms for skill development, social empowerment, and economic mobility. The key areas where SHGs contribute to promoting women’s entrepreneurship in the BTR are outlined below:

4.1. Financial Inclusion and Access to Credit

SHGs act as informal financial institutions, providing women with access to micro-credit and savings facilities that are often unavailable through formal banking channels (Nair, 2012). This access to financial resources allows women to invest in their entrepreneurial ventures, purchase

raw materials, expand operations, and ultimately increase their income. As a result, SHGs help women achieve economic independence and create pathways for financial empowerment (Mughal, 2014). By pooling resources, SHGs offer women the chance to secure small loans that significantly impact their business growth and sustainability (Barman & Chanu, 2016).

4.2. Entrepreneurial Skill Development

SHGs offer essential training programs aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills such as financial management, marketing strategies, and product development (Kumawat & Bansa, 2018). These programs equip women with the tools needed to effectively manage their businesses, making them more sustainable and competitive in the market (Konch, 2016). The continuous learning opportunities foster innovation and allow women to navigate the challenges of entrepreneurship, leading to greater success in their ventures.

4.3. Changing Perceptions and Empowerment

One of the significant contributions of SHGs is the shift in perceptions among women regarding entrepreneurship. Activities traditionally seen as domestic, such as weaving, poultry farming, and piggery, are now viewed as viable and profitable business ventures (Sarma & Barua, 2018). This change in mindset helps break down social and cultural barriers, enhancing women's self-confidence and ability to pursue business opportunities (Pradhani & Chaudhary, 2018). As women see the financial success of these activities, they become more empowered to take control of their economic futures, challenging traditional gender roles.

4.4. Enhanced Confidence and Decision-Making Abilities

Participation in SHGs significantly boosts women's self-confidence and decision-making abilities. Through collective action and leadership roles within their groups, women are empowered to take on greater responsibility, both personally and professionally. This increased self-efficacy enhances their capacity to make informed decisions, improving the management of their businesses and positively influencing their personal lives (Maity & Sarania, 2017).

4.5. Economic Independence and Community Involvement

SHGs provide women with more than just financial support; they offer a platform for community involvement and leadership. By participating in SHGs, women gain the confidence to engage in decision-making processes at the community level, contributing to the broader socio-economic development of their regions (Bisht & Sharma, 1991; Suneetha, 2012). This involvement not only boosts their own economic status but also strengthens the overall welfare of their families and communities. SHGs contribute to elevating not only individual

entrepreneurs but also their households, promoting upward social mobility within their communities (Nair, 2012). By fostering economic resilience, SHGs help create a more inclusive and dynamic regional economy.

5. Challenges to SHGs in Promoting Women's Entrepreneurship in BTR

While Self-Help Groups (SHGs) have made notable progress in promoting women's entrepreneurship in the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR), several significant challenges need to be addressed to sustain and maximize their impact. These challenges span infrastructural, socio-cultural, and operational aspects that limit the growth of SHG-led enterprises.

5.1. Limited Market Access and Infrastructure

- **Poor Infrastructure:** Inadequate transportation networks, unreliable communication facilities, and limited access to technology severely restrict SHG-led enterprises from reaching their full potential. These limitations make it difficult for women to efficiently transport their products, access market information, and expand their customer base (Konch, 2016).
- **Limited Market Information:** Many SHG members lack awareness about key market dynamics such as consumer preferences, pricing strategies, and market trends. This knowledge gap hampers their ability to adapt to market changes, effectively compete, and optimize profits (Sarma & Barua, 2018). Access to reliable market data and consumer insights is crucial for improving competitiveness.

5.2. Gender Stereotypes and Discrimination

- **Patriarchal Norms:** Deep-rooted patriarchal values and societal expectations often restrict women's mobility and limit their decision-making power. This gender bias can hinder women's access to resources and prevent them from fully participating in entrepreneurial activities (Garikipati, 2008). Cultural barriers also limit women's capacity to engage in leadership roles within their SHGs or communities.
- **Limited Family Support:** Women entrepreneurs frequently face resistance from their families, particularly when balancing household responsibilities with running a business. This lack of support can discourage entrepreneurial pursuits and further reinforce traditional gender roles, reducing women's potential for success (Baruah & Borkakati, 1998).

5.3. Sustainability of SHG-Led Enterprises

- **Limited Access to Formal Credit:** Although SHGs offer micro-credit, scaling up businesses often requires larger loans from formal financial institutions. Due to lack of collateral and credit history, SHG members struggle to secure such financing, limiting their ability to invest in long-term growth and expansion (Sarma & Barua, 2018). Access to formal credit remains a critical barrier to the sustainability of SHG-led enterprises.
- **Skill Gaps and Capacity Limitations:** While SHGs provide initial training in basic business skills, many members require continuous learning to adapt to evolving market demands and technological advancements. The lack of ongoing capacity-building initiatives can leave SHG members unprepared to manage complex business operations, affecting the sustainability of their ventures.

5.4. Operational and Management Challenges

- **Lack of Managerial Skills:** Many SHG members lack formal education and experience in managing the operational aspects of their businesses. Deficiencies in financial management, inventory control, and human resource allocation can undermine the overall efficiency and success of SHG-led enterprises (Kumawat & Bansa, 2018). Without structured management practices, growth and sustainability are difficult to achieve.
- **Group Dynamics and Internal Conflicts:** Internal conflicts and power struggles within SHGs can weaken collective decision-making processes and hinder effective resource allocation. Such issues often arise due to differing priorities among members, making it challenging for SHGs to operate cohesively (Sarma & Barua, 2018).
- **Record Keeping and Financial Management:** Maintaining proper financial records and managing accounts can be challenging for SHGs, especially in remote areas where access to technology and financial literacy is limited. Poor financial management practices can lead to inefficiencies and hinder the ability to track profits, ultimately affecting the transparency and sustainability of SHG operations (Barman & Chanu, 2017).

By addressing these challenges, SHGs can continue to empower women entrepreneurs in the BTR and contribute significantly to the region's socio-economic development.

6. Conclusion

Self-help groups (SHGs) have proven to be powerful mechanisms for promoting women's entrepreneurship in the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR). Through financial inclusion, skill

development, and empowerment, SHGs enable women to engage in entrepreneurial activities that improve their economic standing and contribute to community development. Women's participation in SHGs has led to significant positive outcomes, including increased access to credit, enhanced entrepreneurial skills, greater confidence, and improved social mobility. However, persistent challenges such as limited market access, infrastructural constraints, and socio-cultural norms must be addressed to fully realize the potential of SHGs in fostering women's entrepreneurship in the region.

To sustain and amplify the positive impact of SHGs, targeted interventions are required to address these challenges. Infrastructure development, market linkages, and efforts to combat gender discrimination will be critical in ensuring that SHGs continue to empower women entrepreneurs and drive inclusive economic growth in the BTR.

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